

CARBON FIBER REINFORCED SILICON CARBIDE
CERAMIC COMPOSITES VIA POLYMER PYROLYSIS
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ABSTRACT

Carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide ceramic matrix composites have been fabricated by slurry impregnation/polymer pyrolysis route. The preceramic polymer used in this study was polytitanocarbosilane (PTC). The relationships between the nature of the precursor and the processing conditions was investigated. The three point bending fracture behaviour of C/SiC was measured. The experimental results showed that the molecular weight of PTC should be selected appropriately to meet the processing conditions, but it is more suitable to add some crosslinking agents to PTC during the composites processing so as to achieve high yields than to oxide at elevated temperatures as commonly used in the manufacture of SiC fibers. Fiber/matrix interphase must also be modified in carbon fiber/silicon carbide composites.

KEYWORDS: Ceramic Composites; Carbon Fiber/Silicon Carbide; Polymer Pyrolysis; Preceramic Polymer/Polytitanocarbosilane.

1. INTRODUCTION

Utilization of polymer precursors to ceramic matrix composites offers ease of processing at lower temperatures and pressureless sintering, and the opportunity to produce complex-shaped ceramic composite parts as C/C composites. A series of organometallic polymer precursors have been developed successfully during the past decade which can converted to nonoxide ceramics from high temperature pyrolysis(1). The organometallic precursor conversion method provides another route to fabricate ceramic matrix composites (CMC) with more advantages over conventional sintering and powder processing(2).

In this study, a carbon fiber reinforced silicon carbide CMC was fabricated by slurry impregnation/polymer pyrolysis. The preceramic polymer used was polytitanocarbosilane (PTC). The relationships between the nature of the precursor and the processing conditions was investigated. The three point bending fracture behaviour of C/SiC was measured and examed by SEM.

2. EXPERIMENTAL

The polytitanocarbosilane was synthesised in our lab by a one-step process(3). The GPC patterns of the PTC was shown in FIG.1. The GPC curves were measured using Watters-244 with ULYRASTYRA-GEL as a GPC column in toluene solution. The molecular weight and structure of the PTC were controlled to provide a series of polymer precursors. The unidirectional C/SiC laminates were manufactured as described before(4). Commercial SiC powder with average particle size 1μ was used to minimize the shrinkage of the matrix, which was subsequently pyrolysed to 1300°C under N_2 atmosphere to form a ceramic matrix composite. The typical conversion cycle was $1^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 420°C , hold for 1 hr, $0.7^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 800°C , $2^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$ to 1300°C , hold for 2 hrs. The carbon fiber used in this study was a medium strength and medium modulus type. In some cases, surface treatment was made with a pitch solution to determine the effect of fiber/matrix interphase. Reimpregnation of pyrolyzed bars was necessary to increase the density and mechanical properties. Composite samples were vacuum infiltrated in a PTC bath, then removed, heated and pyrolyzed for several times.

The three point bending tests were performed on a mechanical tester with a span of 40 mm. The composite test specimens were 4 mm wide, 3 mm thick, and 50 mm long. The fracture surface of the samples was examed by SEM. Thermal gravatric (TG) analysis was carried out using Rigaku TG-DTA machine in $50\text{ cm}^3/\text{min}$ nitrogen flow up to 1200°C at a heating rate of $10^\circ\text{C}/\text{min}$.

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Relationships Between Molecular Structure of PTC and the Processing Conditions
PTC used in this study was synthesised as following:

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Previous studies(5) showed that the chemical structure of PTC was analogy to that of polycarbosilane (PC) with a planar network, Ti existed in the form of $\text{Ti}(\text{O})_4$ -crosslinking linkage. TABLE 1 list the relationship between \bar{M}_n , \bar{M}_w and pyrolysis yields of PTC with various molecular weight. As seen from TABLE 1, the yield increase with \bar{M}_n of PTC. Promoted yield of polymer precursors is essentially important to make high performance CMC via polymer pyrolysis route. Not only can it decrease the porosity of the composites, minimize the matrix shrinkage, but can promote the densification efficiency. However, the disadvantage of using too much high \bar{M}_n PTC to fabricate CMC is that it would cause the new problem to composite manufacture processing with increased melting point and decreased solution solubility of PTC. Therefore, selection of PTC with appropriate \bar{M}_n is necessary. FIG.2 shows the three point bending strengthes of C/SiC fabricated from the pyrolysis of PTC with different \bar{M}_n . A maximum peak is observed with the increase of \bar{M}_n , which is analogy to that of C/SiC pyrolyzed from PC(6).

3.2 Effects of Crosslinking The Si-H bonds in PTC structure are relatively reactive and can undergo dehydrogenation or demethanation with neighbouring Si-H or Si-CH₃ bonds under certain conditions (eg. heating or γ -ray irradiation), thus leading to the increase of molecular weight or the transformation of 2D planar network to 3D crosslinking network(7). In addition, some organometallic compounds, as titanium tetraisopropoxide in the synthesis of PTC, can readily react with Si-H bonds resulting in the formation of highly crosslinked structure of PTC.

The TG curves of PTC with different crosslinking treatments are shown in FIG.3. As seen from FIG.3, the TG curves consist of three stages. At first stage (<550°C), due to the wide molecular weight distribution of PTC (FIG.1), the evaporation of oligomers causes greater weight loss (22%) in as received PTC samples. For PTC adding Ti(OBu)₄, the weight loss is rapid (12%) at the beginning before 350°C and tends to stable afterwards, showing Ti(OBu)₄ partially crosslinked with PTC. While oxidation-crosslinked PTC shows almost no weight loss (1%). During the second stage (550-750°C), the yields are similar in spite of different treatments. Finally, between 750-1200°C, the slope of TG curves are more or less the same.

The above results indicate that the key of controlling the final pyrolysis yields is mainly at the first stage, i.e. the amount of oligomers. To confirm this assumption we have slowly heated PTC to 470°C in N₂ atmosphere to remove the oligomers and to make the PTC fully crosslinked. The TG curve of the resulting crosslinked PTC is shown in FIG.3. It is very similar to that of above oxidation-crosslinked PTC. Therefore, it seems more significant to choose effective crosslinking agents such as Ti(OBu)₄ so as to increase the molecular weight and crosslinking density of preceramic polymers during the CMC processing. Whereas the commonly used oxidation crosslinking in the manufacture of SiC fibers is inadequate to that of SiC matrix composites, especially when the density of CMC is fairly high.

3.3 Carbon Fiber/Silicon Carbide Interphase TABLE 2 list the changes of density and bending strength of unidirectional C/SiC with impregnations. The strength and density of C/SiC increase with reimpregnations. But the failure mode turns from ductile to brittle behaviour. The pull-out length of the fracture surfaces become shorter with the increase of reimpregnations (FIG.4), which means reimpregnation results in a strong interfacial bonding between carbon fiber and silicon carbide matrix and decrease the toughness of the CMC.

To determine the effect of a weak fiber/matrix interphase, a pitch solution was applied to carbon fibers prior to impregnating with preceramic polymer slurry and copolymerized with PTC. A carbon coated carbon fiber/silicon carbide composite was produced. Altering the fiber/matrix interphase significantly enhanced strength and toughness simultaneously (see FIG.5). SEM observations showed that failure were typically noncatastrophic with large amounts of fiber pullout on the fracture surface of carbon coated C/SiC composite (FIG.6).

4. CONCLUSIONS

Utilization of organometallic polymer precursor pyrolysis is a very promising route to fabricate ceramic matrix composites. Factors which must be considered for a successful application of this method to fabricate CMC include polymer structure and pyrolysis conditions. High yields are desirable but it is more suitable to use an appropriate crosslinking agent than to oxidize at elevated temperature. Fiber/matrix interphase must also be carefully controlled in order to achieve the best performance of CMC.

5. REFERENCES

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TABLE 1 Relationships between \bar{M}_n , T_m and Pyrolysis Yields of PTC

sample	\bar{M}_n	dispersity	T_m (°C)	yield(%)
PTC-1	1534	2.38	225-240	74.0
PTC-2	1223	2.36	150-160	71.4
PTC-3	1189	2.40	140-155	71.0
PTC-4	1004	2.35	105-130	69.7
PTC-5	926	2.42	82-93	68.6
PTC-6	879	2.43	71-84	62.3

TABLE 2 Changes of Bending Strength and Density with reimpregnations

impregnation times	density (g/cm ³)	strength (MPa)
0	1.551	99.3
1	1.627	108.0
2	1.794	154.9
3	1.848	216.7

FIG.2 Flexural strength of C/SiC from PTC

FIG.3 TG curves of PTC with different treatments
 A-250 °C/1hr oxidation; B-adding $Ti(OBu)_4$
 C-as received; D-crosslinked PTC ($N_2, 470^\circ C$)

FIG.5 The P- ϵ curves of C/SiC
 A-pitch solution coating
 B-surface untreated

FIG.4 The fracture surfaces of C/SiC
 impregnation time: (1)0, (2)2, (3)4

FIG.6 SEM observation of C/SiC with and without fiber coating

